

Extraction chromatographic studies of aluminium(III) with *n*-capric acid

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A selective method has been developed for extraction chromatographic studies of Al^{III} with *n*-capric acid (liquid cation exchanger) coated on silica gel as stationary phase. Quantitative extraction of Al^{III} has been achieved at pH 3.5–5.5. The effect of different acids with varying concentrations, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution have been investigated. Al^{III} has been separated from binary, ternary and many other multicomponent mixtures as well as from ores and alloy samples.

High molecular mass carboxylic acids viz. Versatic-10¹ have been used in solvent extraction technique for extraction and separation of aluminium. But such a method, however, suffers emulsification problem² as well as it is difficult to strip metal from organic phase and the process is time consuming³. Chromatographic methods, particularly, dynamically modified reverse phase sorbent system (RPEC) have been attractive for this purpose. The present study describes the systematic extraction chromatographic behaviour of aluminium(III) with high molecular mass carboxylic acid, *n*-capric acid (decanoic acid) coated on silica gel. The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and free from limitations mentioned above. By this method it was also possible to separate aluminium(III) from ore and alloy samples.

Results and discussion

The extraction chromatographic behaviour of Al^{III} with *n*-capric acid coated on silica gel showed that Al^{III} is quantitatively extracted at pH 3.5–5.5. Common anions like nitrate, sulphate, chloride do not interfere in the extraction. pH 4.8 was used as extraction condition for further studies.

Stripping agents : Different concentrations of nitric acid, hydrochloric acid, acetic acid, ammonium nitrate, sodium nitrate, ammonium chloride and demineralised water were tested. It was observed that quantitative recovery of Al^{III} is possible with HNO_3 (up to 0.1 *M*), HCl (0.5 *M* and onwards) and acetic acid (0.5 *M* and onwards). Of these eluents 0.1 *M* HNO_3 gave best elution and hence it was used as eluent for further steps of experiment.

Separation of Al^{III} from binary mixture : In binary mixtures with Al^{III} at pH 4.8, Ce^{IV} , Zn^{II} , Co^{II} , Cr^{III} , Mg^{II} and Ni^{II} passed through the column with mobile phase. Extracted Al^{III} was, however, eluted with 0.1 *M* HNO_3 and estimated

complexometrically with EDTA. Binary mixtures containing Zr^{IV} , In^{III} , Tl^{III} , Ga^{III} , Pd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Th^{IV} , Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Fe^{III} , Pb^{II} along with Al^{III} were passed separately through the column at pH 4.8 where all the diverse metal ions were co-extracted with Al^{III} . Th^{IV} , Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Fe^{III} and Pb^{II} were eluted with 0.01 *M* HCl . Hg^{II} was eluted with 0.5 *M* NH_4NO_3 . Finally Al^{III} was eluted with 0.1 *M* HNO_3 . In case of separation of In^{III} , Ga^{III} and Pd^{II} from Al^{III} , the mother metal (Al^{III}) was eluted first with 0.1 *M* HNO_3 followed by the elution of other metals with perchloric acid. After separation, metal ions were estimated complexometrically using EDTA. Extraction kinetics of Al^{III} with respect to *n*-capric acid was found to be fast.

Separation of Al^{III} from multicomponent mixtures : Separation of Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} and Al^{III} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at pH 4.8, only Cr^{III} passed through the column with mobile phase. The rest of the metal ions were extracted. Fe^{III} was eluted first with 0.01 *M* HCl followed by the elution of Al^{III} with 0.1 *M* HNO_3 . Separation of Al^{III} , In^{III} and Tl^{III} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at pH 4.8, all the metal ions were extracted. Al^{III} was eluted first with 0.1 *M* HNO_3 followed by the elution of Tl^{III} with 1 *M* NH_4Cl . Finally In^{III} was eluted with 0.5 *M* perchloric acid. Separation of Al^{III} , Ga^{III} and Tl^{III} was achieved by passing the ternary mixture through the column at pH 4.8. All the metal ions were extracted. Al^{III} was eluted first with 0.1 *M* HNO_3 followed by the elution of Tl^{III} with 1 *M* NH_4Cl and finally Ga^{III} was eluted with 0.5 *M* perchloric acid. Separation of Co^{II} , Fe^{III} and Al^{III} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at pH 4.8. Co^{II} percolated with the mobile phase. Rest of the metal ions were extracted. Fe^{III} was eluted with 0.01 *M* HCl followed by the elution of

Al^{III} with 0.1 M HNO₃. Separation of Zn^{II}, Fe^{III} and Al^{III} was achieved by passing the solution through the column at pH 4.8. Only Zn^{II} percolated with mobile phase. Fe^{III} eluted first with 0.01 M HCl and then Al^{III} with 0.1 M HNO₃. Separation of Ce^{IV}, Zr^{IV} and Al^{III} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at pH 4.8. Ce^{IV} percolated with mobile phase. Zr^{IV} and Al^{III} extracted. Zr^{IV} was eluted with 4 M HNO₃ followed by the elution of Al^{III} with 0.1 M HNO₃. Separation of Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at pH 4.8. All the metal ions were extracted. Fe^{III} eluted first with 0.01 M HCl then Al^{III} with 0.1 M HNO₃. Tl^{III} with 1 M NH₄Cl and finally In^{III} with 0.5 M perchloric acid. Separation of Cr^{III}, Al^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at pH 4.9. Only Cr^{III} percolated with mobile phase. The rest of the metal ions were extracted. Al^{III} was eluted first with 0.1 M HNO₃ followed by the elution of Tl^{III} with 1 M NH₄Cl and finally In^{III} was eluted with 0.5 M perchloric acid. Separation of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III} was achieved by passing the multicomponent mixture through column at pH 4.8. Only Cr^{III} percolated with mobile phase. The rest of the metal ions were extracted. Fe^{III} was eluted first with 0.01 M HCl then Al^{III} with 0.1 M HNO₃, Tl^{III} with 1 M NH₄Cl and finally In^{III} with 0.5 M perchloric acid.

Separation of Zn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and Tl^{III} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at pH 4.8. Zn^{II} passed through the column, other metal ions were extracted. Fe^{III} was eluted first with 0.01 M HCl then Al^{III} with 0.1 M HNO₃. Tl^{III} with 1 M NH₄Cl and finally Ga^{III} with 0.5 M perchloric acid respectively. Results achieved were presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Separation of Al^{III} from multicomponent synthetic mixture

Metal ions in mixture	Wt. added mg	Recovery %	Relative error %	Eluent used
Cr ^{III}	1.7	98.1	-1.9	-
Fe ^{III}	1.4	98.6	-1.4	0.01 M HCl
Al ^{III}	0.85	101.1	+1.1	0.1 M HNO ₃
Al ^{III}	0.85	100.0	0	0.1 M HNO ₃
Tl ^{III}	5.5	99.6	-0.4	1 M NH ₄ Cl
In ^{III}	2.71	100.7	+0.7	0.5 M HClO ₄
Al ^{III}	0.85	98.9	-1.1	0.1 M HNO ₃
Tl ^{III}	5.5	100.8	+0.8	1 M NH ₄ Cl
Ga ^{III}	1.02	101.9	+1.9	0.5 M HClO ₄
Co ^{II}	1.02	100.0	0	-
Fe ^{III}	1.4	101.2	+1.2	0.1 M HNO ₃
Al ^{III}	0.85	101.2	+1.2	0.1 M HNO ₃
Ce ^{IV}	2.52	98.8	-1.2	-
Zr ^{IV}	1.45	102.0	+2	4 M HNO ₃
Al ^{III}	0.85	100.0	0	0.1 M HNO ₃

Table-1 (contd.)

Zn ^{II}	1.71	100.5	+0.5	-
Fe ^{III}	1.4	99.2	-0.8	0.01 M HCl
Al ^{III}	0.85	100.0	0	0.1 M HNO ₃
Fe ^{III}	1.4	98.5	-1.5	0.01 M HCl
Al ^{III}	0.85	98.9	-1.1	0.1 M HNO ₃
Tl ^{III}	5.5	99.8	-0.2	1 M NH ₄ Cl
In ^{III}	2.71	100.7	+0.7	0.5 M HClO ₄
Cr ^{III}	1.07	100.0	0	-
Al ^{III}	0.85	100.0	0	0.1 M HNO ₃
Tl ^{III}	5.5	99.2	-0.8	1 M NH ₄ Cl
In ^{III}	2.71	100.5	+0.5	0.5 M HClO ₄
Cr ^{III}	1.07	97.2	-2.8	-
Fe ^{III}	1.4	101.4	+1.4	0.01 M HCl
Al ^{III}	0.85	99.4	-0.6	0.1 M HNO ₃
Tl ^{III}	5.5	100	0	1 M NH ₄ Cl
In ^{III}	2.71	100	0	0.5 M HClO ₄
Zn ^{II}	1.71	99.4	-0.6	-
Fe ^{III}	1.4	97.6	-2.4	0.01 M HCl
Al ^{III}	0.85	98.9	-1.1	0.1 M HNO ₃
Tl ^{III}	5.5	101.4	+1.4	1 M NH ₄ Cl
Ga ^{III}	1.02	101.0	+1.0	0.5 M HClO ₄

Separation of Al^{III} from ore and alloy : The proposed method was applied for the extraction of Al^{III} from standard ore (bauxite) and alloy sample. In both the cases encouraging results were achieved. The results are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Determination of Al^{III} from ore and alloy sample

Ore and alloy	Composition sample	Amount recovered %	Error %
Bauxite	SiO ₂ = 1.67	50.69	~1.0
	TiO ₂ = 2.25		
	Al ₂ O ₃ = 51.2		
	Fe ₂ O ₃ = 17.5		
	CaO = 0.05		
	MgO = 0.03		
Brass (10 g)	Cu = 60.8	3.28	0.91
	Sn = 0.21		
	Zn = 32.0		
	Pb = 0.23		
	Ni = 0.16		
	Fe = 1.56		
	Al = 3.31		
	Mn = 1.36		

Experimental

An Elico Li-120 pH meter with a combined glass electrode and a chromatographic column (Borosil) were used.

The liquid cation exchanger *n*-capric acid, a high molecular mass synthetic carboxylic acid (decanoic acid) was used. A stock solution of Al^{III} was prepared in distilled water and standardised complexometrically using xylenol orange³ indicator. The ion exchange material was prepared following literature method⁴. The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger was determined as per standard method⁵ and was found to be 2.04 meq. of H⁺/g at 25°.

Extraction procedure : A solution of pH 4.8, prepared with ammonium acetate/acetic acid was passed through the

column (0.8×6.5 cm) containing the prepared exchanger (3 g). An aliquot of solution containing 0.85 mg of Al^{III} was passed through the column at pH 4.8 with a flow rate 1 ml min^{-1} . After extraction, Al^{III} was stripped with different acids, salts of various concentrations and demineralised water. 0.1 M HNO_3 was found to be the best stripping agent. The amount of Al^{III} was determined complexometrically⁶.

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